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Comparing SYCL data transfer strategies for tracking use cases

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Abstract.

The aim of this work is to compare the performance and ease of programming of the various data transfer strategies provided by SYCL 2020: *buffers/accessors* on one hand and the different storage types exposed by *Unified Shared Memory* (USM) on the other hand. We measured the relative performance of USM exclusively located either on the host (*USM host*) or on the device (*USM device*), or automatically managed and moved (*USM shared*). We also tried to quantify the impact of formatting data in a GPU-friendly manner as opposed to using a regular pointer-based structure in which the C++ allocator was replaced by the SYCL allocator `sycl::malloc`. We first made a PCIe-bound micro-benchmark to test the SYCL memory models with a simple access pattern. We then switched to a real use-case provided by Traccc, a research project associated to the ACTS particle tracking library. The algorithm of interest is SparseCCL, a clustering algorithm used on the first step of track reconstruction. For consistency, all tests were made on a single hardware architecture: a recent server having a discrete GPU with dedicated VRAM, representative of the hardware currently used by the ACTS team.

1. Introduction

ACTS is an experiment-independent C++ toolkit for charged particle track reconstruction in high energy physics experiments. Within this context, the Traccc project investigates how to take advantage of the increased variety of available hardware at CERN, such as GPUs. How to efficiently make existing code run on accelerators is an open-ended question, both performance-wise and in terms of time spent writing software.

SYCL is a royalty-free, cross-platform abstraction layer that enables code for heterogeneous processors to be written using standard ISO C++17 with the host and kernel code for an application contained in the same source file. SYCL also provides two memory models (USM and *buffers/accessors*) allowing for CPU data-structures to be used almost untouched on GPUs, yet also allowing data-structures to be formatted in a GPU-friendly way.

By using SYCL, we will try to evaluate the impact of using almost untouched CPU data-structures for GPUs, compared to data-structures commonly used for GPU programming, both with a simplified benchmark and with a real life algorithm from Traccc. We will also compare the different memory models offered by SYCL.

Every benchmark was run on the same system: a Debian GNU/Linux 11.0 based server with 512 GB DDR4-2400, an AMD EPYC 7502 CPU with 32 cores, 64 threads, a PCIe 3.0

x16 bus with a theoretical bandwidth of 16 GB/s and an NVIDIA Quadro RTX 5000 having 16 GB GDDR6 and a theoretical memory bandwidth of 448 GB/s. The SYCL code was run by hipSYCL 0.9.1-20210702 amd64, using the CUDA 10.1 back-end. We felt hipSYCL to be an interesting SYCL implementation to try out first, rather than the more mainstream Data Parallel C++ (DPC++) from Intel, as the SYCL standard was made to avoid monopoly from any single implementation. HipSYCL also proved to be easier to install on our server.

2. Micro-benchmark

We first made a simple micro-benchmark to analyze the relative performance of the SYCL memory models in a controlled environment and compare it to theoretical expectations from hardware specifications. In this benchmark, the GPU kernel performs a simple data reduction task: each thread computes the sum of 128 4-byte floating-point numbers from a single vector consisting of about 1.6 billion randomly generated floats (6 GiB of data, 6.44 GB), without synchronization between threads. The resulting sums are then read from the host and summed by the CPU. This makes for 6 GiB of input data sent to the GPU, and 48 MiB (50 MB) of retrieved data. The value of 128 elements summed per thread was chosen since it brought the best performance. The overall benchmark execution time will thus be mostly dictated by PCIe data transfer rates: kernel execution time, when it can be separated from PCIe transfer times, is memory-bound. The same kernel is launched twice, with the same input data, to emphasize what work is done in a lazy manner.

	alloc native	alloc sycl	fill	copy	ker ₁	ker ₂	dealloc sycl	dealloc native	total
USM device	696	9	1074	551	17	17	7	16	2387
accessors	699	0.1	1074	-	585	17	7	16	2398
USM shared	-	0.1	2076	-	1471	17	679	-	4243
USM host	-	1757	1075	-	507	506	800	-	4645

Figure 1. Elapsed time in milliseconds for the main steps of the micro-benchmark. The table distinguishes the timing of native and SYCL allocations and deallocations, although they are grouped in the graph. Native allocations are made with a classic C allocator `new array_name[size]` while SYCL allocations are made using `sycl::malloc_(device/shared/host)`. The input data is filled beforehand into native memory for *USM device* and *buffers/accessors* options, or directly into SYCL memory for *USM host* or *USM shared* options. The explicit copy step of *USM device* is distinguished in the table, although grouped with first kernel execution in the graph.

USM device has the benefit that all steps are clearly separated, which lets us check the hardware characteristics. As seen in Figure 1, the explicit copy from the host to the device takes 551 ms to complete, accounting for an observed PCIe bandwidth of about 12 GB/s, lower than the theoretical 16 GB/s, but according to NVIDIA experts, this may be expected. On alternative benchmarks we discovered that this allocation is sometimes lazy, making the allocation faster and the copy longer. The kernel is then processed in 17 ms, leading to a deduced memory bandwidth for the GPU of about 380 GB/s, relatively close to the theoretical 448 GB/s of this GPU. As far as USM goes, *USM device* is overall the most efficient way of dealing with this kind of memory-bound program.

The *buffers/accessors* approach is the oldest and highest-level way of managing data, as it relies on a task dependency graph, leaving data transfer scheduling entirely up to the SYCL implementation. Its overall performance profile is very similar to that of *USM device*, but the data transfer is performed in a lazy way when data is first accessed (GPU kernel run 1).

However, these two options have some technical limitations:

- Input data must be organized in large contiguous arrays;
- Input data must fit into GPU memory, or fragmentation must be performed manually;
- Input data must be prepared in a host-accessible memory allocation.

These limitations do not apply to *USM host* and *USM shared* options. One can directly allocate SYCL memory areas, and fill them with input data from CPU code, without concern for size or presence of pointers as the latter can be used from both CPU and GPU code. Yet this comes with a price. *USM host* SYCL allocation is expensive, and the data must be transferred from host to device each time it is accessed, as demonstrated by the kernel run 2. Usage of *USM host* may therefore only be recommended in use cases where data is accessed only once and allocations can be reused.

In contrast, *USM shared* exhibits negligible allocation overhead, but the automatic data migration process significantly impacts both the fill and kernel steps. By profiling the execution of this program using NVIDIA's Visual Profiler (nvvp), we found that the memory copy still goes on in an asynchronous way until the first kernel has ended. The SYCL implementation does not know we need to access memory in a respectively read-only and write-only mode. This results in a large number of page faults, that only finish once the whole dataset has been accessed by the first kernel run. The *USM shared* synchronization mechanisms, together with the API providing the implementation of no awareness of the access patterns that we are going to perform, also makes deallocation expensive.

All in all, *USM device* and *buffers/accessors* remain the best options, as long as the input data is made of big flat contiguous arrays, and fits into the GPU memory. If not, *USM shared* can be helpful, but at the steep price of halving execution performance (for this benchmark, hardware and SYCL implementation). Finally, usage of *USM host* seems rarely relevant, except for secondary data that is rarely accessed.

3. SparseCCL

SparseCCL is an algorithm specifically designed for HEP tracking. It is in charge of the very first stage of track reconstruction: the connected component labeling also known as clustering. Its memory access pattern is more complex than that of our micro-benchmark, and represents a more realistic usage of the SYCL API, with multiple access to the data. This section still aims to compare the relative performance of the various USM allocation types, together with the *buffers/accessors* technique.

3.1. SparseCCL with flat arrays

We started to structure the data in a relatively device-friendly fashion. It is flattened into 2 large contiguous arrays, easily copyable to and from the device: one for the input data and one for the output, accounting for respectively 1664 MB and 833 MB. Results are shown on Figure 2.

The *USM host* kernel takes a very long time to execute because instead of accessing device local memory, or even caches, an I/O request on the PCIe bus is issued each time the kernel needs to access memory, leading to extremely poor performance. To avoid masking the difference between the other options, we therefore opted not to display in in the graph.

With that outlier out of the way, the comparison of the three other options ends up qualitatively similar to the micro-benchmark case. The main quantitative difference is that since this is a real application, with larger computations and larger reuse of input data, the extra cost of *USM shared* becomes more acceptable, given the greater ease of coding. As a matter of fact, coding is made easier since the memory allocated with the pointer-oriented `sycl::malloc_shared` is usable both on the host (CPU-only code) and on the device (sycl kernel), making the use of CPU data-structures possible even in kernels, without any need to reorganize it. Indeed, pointers returned by `sycl::malloc_shared` are both valid on the host and device code.

	alloc native	alloc sycl	fill	copy	ker ₁	ker ₂	dealloc sycl	dealloc native	total
USM device	267	4	564	141	137	137	7	5	1262
accessors	266	0.01	564	-	284	138	6	6	1264
USM shared	-	0.09	845	-	442	138	264	-	1689
USM host	-	697	567	-	44859	44801	339	-	91263

Figure 2. Elapsed time in milliseconds for the main steps of the SparseCCL memory management, and two iterations of clustering (ker₁ and ker₂). Data is flattened into big arrays during the fill step. For readability, *USM host* has not been shown in the graph.

3.2. SparseCCL: flat arrays versus pointer graph

Flattening data to make it usable by any device is not a hard technical requirement. With the *USM shared* and *USM host* allocation types, pointers can be used both on device and on the host. As a result, almost any CPU computation could be made to run on devices supported by SYCL, without changes to its data structures, provided some changes are made to the computation algorithms to take advantage of hardware parallelism. To make the data accessible by the host and the device, it is only necessary to change the regular C++ allocators, such as `malloc` or `new`, to a `sycl::malloc_host` or `sycl::malloc_shared` allocator.

	alloc native	alloc sycl	fill	copy	ker ₁	ker ₂	dealloc sycl	dealloc native	total
USM shared flat	-	0.09	845	-	442	138	264	-	1689
USM shared ptr	-	59531	1152	-	742	190	34507	-	96122
USM host flat	-	697	567	-	44859	44801	339	-	91263
USM host ptr	-	57657	655	-	55122	55144	24384	-	192962
cpu flat	267	-	566	-	1807	1807	-	5	4452
cpu ptr	390	-	567	-	1959	1970	-	225	5111

Figure 3. Comparison between the use of a flat data structure consisting of few big flat arrays and that of a pointer graph. The time unit is milliseconds.

The performance implications of such a change are shown in Figure 3. As can be seen, the most severe impact of this change is by far on memory allocation and deallocation times, which increase by orders of magnitude. This is to be expected, since as mentioned before, the "flat" version only requires 4 arrays to be allocated with SYCL *USM shared*, host or with a regular *malloc*. The pointer graph version, in contrast, requires about 4 million allocations to complete the graph, and the underlying memory allocation mechanism is clearly performing a lot more efficiently when performing a couple large memory allocations as opposed to a large amount of small memory allocations. It should also be noted that in this data layout, reusing memory allocations is a lot more difficult, which makes the observed impact hard to amortize.

In a CPU-only implementation of the same algorithm, going from a flat 1D structure to a pointer graph has a much smaller impact on performance, except for the deallocation step which is much longer. This hints at the fact that CPU allocators deal a bit more gracefully with large amounts of small allocation requests.

Compared to this, the fill and kernel times are a lot less affected, by a factor of 1.5 at most. From these observations, it follows that while replacing the usual *malloc* with a `sycl::malloc_shared` may produce a working program, using many small allocations comes at a prohibitive cost that will usually more than negate the performance benefits of performing computation using a GPU.

4. Conclusions

SYCL is an emerging standard for heterogeneous computing with a sophisticated memory management API. We showed that on a simple micro-benchmark with data already formatted in a very few big arrays, *USM device* and the *buffers/accessors* were clearly the most efficient ways of handling data. Regarding *USM shared*, easiest to use but unaware of the direction of data transfers, its extra cost depends on the balance between needed data transfers and computations. Finally, even if replacing the usual C++ allocator with a SYCL `sycl::malloc_shared/host` makes for a functioning program, the SYCL allocator proved to have very poor performance when asked to perform a large number of small allocations for a reason to be determined properly. An issue the CPU allocator provided by *glibc* does not seem to have.

5. Future work

Due to time constraints, this preliminary work focused on a single hardware architecture and a single implementation (*hipSYCL*) and backend (NVIDIA CUDA 10.1 running on an NVIDIA Quadro RTX 5000 GPU). A broader list of devices, implementations and backends will be studied in the near future, such as the Intel OneAPI Data Parallel C++ implementation of the SYCL standard, and more devices like AMD discrete graphic cards and Intel and AMD integrated graphic processors, from different generations. Other use-cases will also be tested, including

next steps of the ACTS track reconstruction chain such as seeding, to explore a broader range of data access patterns.

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